

Exploration of Mentoring Experiences of Library Professionals in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil Kano State, Nigeria through the Model of Antecedents, Criteria and Consequences of Mentoring

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Abstract

Given the specialized skills required in police and security-focused library services, mentoring plays a critical role in the professional development of librarians. Within this context, this study was aimed to examine the mentoring experiences of library professionals in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria, using the Model of Antecedents, Criteria, and Consequences of Mentoring. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, using self-structured questionnaire. A census approach was used; therefore the entire population was studied. The study was guided by six research objectives and research questions. Data were analysed using simple percentages, frequency counts, arithmetic means, and Standard Deviations. Findings revealed that the library professionals had engaged in a variety of mentoring strategies. Antecedents of mentoring were rated effective. The library staff reported a positive perception of the mentoring criteria or activities. Consequences or outcome of mentoring were perceived as highly positive. Challenges to effective mentoring were acknowledged, among which are: absence of well-structured organizational policy framework supporting mentoring activities in the library and lack of well-structured mentoring strategies in the library. Respondents recognized regular training for both mentors and mentees on mentoring relationships as one of the major strategies for overcoming challenges to effective mentoring. Based on the findings, the study concludes that the staff members of Nigeria Police Academy Wudil Library, Kano have a positive perception of their mentoring experiences. Among other recommendations, the study emphasized development and implementation of a comprehensive and well-structured mentoring policy to enhance the long-term effectiveness of mentoring practices.

Keywords: *Mentoring, LIS Professionals, Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria, Antecedent-Criteria-Consequences (ACC) Model, Professional Development*

Introduction

Mentoring is an invaluable component in the professional development of library and information personnel, because it provides support, guidance, and knowledge transfer essential for career progression and effective library service delivery. The process of mentoring involves knowledge and experience sharing, provision of emotional support, role modeling and guiding (Mijares, Baxley & Bond, 2013). In specialized institutions like the Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria, library professionals are central to supporting the academic needs of cadets, faculty members, researchers, and the teaming staff of the Academy. Therefore, they require a unique blend of skills to address these specific demands.

Within this context, mentoring assumes a heightened importance, given the unique demands and specialized focus of police education and training. Library professionals are expected to handle information needs related to community policing, criminal investigation, criminal justice, forensic investigation, law, and security studies, areas that require precision, ethical considerations, and confidentiality. Effective mentoring not only equips mentees with the technical skills, such as cataloging and research assistance but also helps to instill an understanding of the ethical standards and specialized competencies required in this special setting. Consequently, mentoring within the Academy library's context is not just about skill acquisition but also about aligning the professional goals of library staff with the core values and mission of the Academy. Academic librarians need to be recognized and valued as professionals who make a positive impact on campus, thus contributing to the academic success and growth of their institution (Burke & Tumbleson, 2019).

Hamilton, Boman, Rubin, and Sahota (2018) point out those mentoring programmes, among other accruable benefits, contribute to improved self-efficacy and confidence among mentees thus, helping them approach complex tasks with greater competence. This is particularly important in environments like the Nigeria Police Academy, where library staff may be required to support academic research in sensitive areas, work with specialized databases, and assist in academic research and security information management. Mentoring can facilitate these skills, offering new staff a guided entry into their roles and helping them integrate effectively into the Academy's specialized environment.

Mentoring within the Nigeria Police Academy library is crucial for supporting library professionals' development and ensuring that they meet the Academy's unique information demands. New library staff members may face challenges adapting to the specific environment of the Academy, where they need to understand both general library practices and specialized knowledge pertinent to police and security studies. Against this background, this study aims to examine the mentoring experiences of the library professionals in Nigeria Police Academy Library, Wudil, Kano, through the lens of the Model of Antecedent, Criteria, and Consequences of mentoring, postulated by Mijares, Baxley, and Bond (2013).

Literature Review

Mentoring is a dynamic partnership that empowers personal and professional growth through mutual learning and guidance between a mentor and mentee (Freedman, 2021). Mentoring in

librarianship is the process of learning and development based on a personal relationship in which an experienced librarian helps a new librarian to develop as a professional and achieve professional goals (Udo-Anyanwu, 2022). According to Ubogu (2019), mentorship is a crucial part of librarians' job aimed at maintaining and improving their professional practice and stay up to date with emerging trends in the field. Wasim, Haroon, Shahid and Wasim (2025), postulate that mentoring involves a relationship where a more experienced individual provides guidance and trusted advice to a less-experienced individual. Mentoring is vital to the success, competency, leadership development and accomplishment of a career in librarianship in contemporary world today.

Ozioko, Echezona and Osadebe (2012) defined mentoring as a process where a senior librarian, referred to as mentor in this context, and a junior librarian referred to as a mentee build a healthy professional relationship with the aim of helping the junior librarian to grow in the career. Nwabueze and Ozioko (2012) also argues that no institution can exist without the older and more experienced members passing on wisdom acquired over the years to new members. A mentor should therefore be a trustworthy, reliable, knowledgeable and well-exposed person.

The primary goal of mentoring in librarianship is to achieve career excellence, thus mentoring entails meeting professional goals. While learning, growth and development may occur in many different types of work and close personal relationships, mentoring relationships are unique because their primary focus is on career growth and development (Ragins & Kram, 2019). Mentoring is vital to career success of an individual; it strengthens the professional and organizational goal (Colosimo, Desmeules, & McKinnon, 2017). Mentoring programmes in academic libraries are usually specific and are closely tied to the librarian's career stage (Freedman, 2021).

There are various types of mentoring that take place in an organization, depending on the structure, goal and policies in place. However mentoring strategies are categorized into formal and informal mentoring. Sodipe and Madukoma (2013) categorize these strategies into two: traditional form which is informal, and the formal mentoring which assumes different forms such as: peer group and electronic mentoring. Informal mentoring is said to occur when a more experienced person takes interest in a less experienced staff with great potentials and talents. It can also occur when a less experienced staff approach a more experienced colleague in order to learn and gain new knowledge and skills from the colleague.

Formal mentoring on the other hand is usually initiated by an organization with the expectation that both mentees and mentors will participate and benefit. Formal mentoring however may have some underlying disadvantages as both parties merged may not be able to foster a good relationship because of individual differences. The success of formal mentoring relationship depends on the matching of the mentor and the mentee. Ritchie and Genoni (2008) observed that formal mentoring is based on structured programme that has an organized context. It gives participants the procedures and guidelines with which to conduct their relationships. For effective mentoring to take place, the mentor should possess a wide variety of characteristics to facilitate a positive mentor- mentee relationship. Some of these characteristics according to Ozioko, Echezona, and Osadebe (2012) include patience, enthusiasm, knowledge sense of humor and respect. Mentoring is one of the ways of knowledge sharing, which offers numerous benefits to both the mentor and

the mentee. According to Wang and Noel (2010) Knowledge sharing is the movement of knowledge among individuals in organizations to help and collaborate with others for problem solving, developing new ideas or implementing policies or procedures.

Mentoring relationships is usually beneficial to the mentor, mentee and even to the organization. As Nigerian Police Academy Library Kano continues to evolve, mentoring remains essential to the growth and professional career development of the staff. They offer valuable wisdom, share expert insights, and help mentees develop long lasting skills for long-term success. According to Chua, et al. (2020), mentoring programs have been linked to various faculty benefits, such as enhanced recruitment, increased engagement, successful faculty promotions, improved retention rates, earlier career achievements, and positive perceptions of the institution's commitment to its faculty. Mentoring programs have also been linked to various faculty benefits, such as enhanced recruitment, increased engagement, successful faculty promotions, improved retention rates, earlier career achievements, and positive perceptions of the institution's commitment to its faculty (Chua, et al, 2020). Idoku et al., (2016) outline the following benefits of mentoring: it develops learning opportunities, gives analytical and reflective skills, develops organizational and professional knowledge and also reinforces self-confidence and willingness to take risks, offers ability to accept criticism and accelerate professional development. According to Ubogu (2019) mentoring programmes in the university boost individuals and team commitments and permit individuals to gain greater insight into library's working. It helps to increase communication with other library staff, helps to change organizational culture to better level, gives individuals the chance to meet different people within the library and network and improve level of performance success.

Furthermore, one of the advantages of mentoring is that it is a two-way process where the mentor can teach the mentee and also learn from the mentee. Olutoyin and Olaniyi (2023) opine that academic librarians benefit from mentoring because it prepares aspiring librarians for the more difficult work that lies ahead. The emergence of new technologies and ways of interacting with information also means that librarians are faced with a changing world of information and must adapt in order to be relevant to the system because users are making new demands that have to be met for effective service delivery. With this changing work environment and growing wants of the user, there is the need for effective mentoring that will allow the librarian fit into her role thereby building her capacity to effectively carry out her duties.

Mentoring, like any other staff development programme also encounters some challenges. David-West and Nmecha (2019) identified lack of sincere desire to share knowledge by the mentor, and inability of both the mentor and the mentee to keep to goals and objectives of the relationship as challenges of mentorship. Nwabueze and Anike (2016) identified unconstructive criticism of mentors, broken confidentially by both the mentor and the mentee, absence mentoring orientation in librarianship as challenges encountered in mentoring among librarians. Similarly Fasola and Mamudu (2020) found out that the major challenges of mentoring were the issue of broken confidence in both the mentor and mentee, absence of mentoring orientation in the practice of librarianship, lack of orientation of librarian on the need for mentoring. Brewerton (2010) concluded that as with any staff development programme, there will always be challenges which include: inability to keep plans, the mentee becoming too dependent on the mentor for all decisions, development of inappropriate emotional feelings as a result of the close nature of the

relationships, and professional jealousy from colleagues. There are notable challenges in creating and implementing effective mentorship initiatives especially in low-middle income countries. These include: time constraints for faculties and students, lack of financial and professional incentives for faculty members, and lack of structured curriculum (Deng, Gulseren, Turner, 2022; Mbouamba, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

This study was framed by the Model of Antecedents, Criteria, and Consequences of Mentoring, developed by Mijares, Baxley, and Bond (2013), adapting Walker and Avant’s (2011) approach which reviewed literature from various disciplines, e.g., Nursing, Anthropology, Business, Education, Psychology and Social Work to offer a nuanced and balanced examination of the concept of mentoring. Through a comprehensive process, the antecedents, criteria, and consequences of mentoring were compiled, analysed, and refined, ultimately yielding operational and theoretical definitions of the concept of mentoring. The concept analysis of mentoring, encompassing its antecedents, mentoring activities, and consequences, has been extensively utilized to inform and enhance mentoring practices. Therefore, a successful mentoring programme is anchored on these three components (Freedman, 2021). Figure 1 presents the diagram illustrating the relationship among the antecedents, criteria, and consequences of mentoring.

Figure 1: *The Model of Antecedents, Criteria, and Consequences of Mentoring*

Source: Mijares, Baxley, and Bond (2013).

Figure 2: *The Antecedents, Criteria, and Consequences of Mentoring*

Source: *Adapted from Mijares, Baxley, and Bond (2013)*

According to the proponents of this model, the mentoring antecedents involve an experienced mentor and an inexperienced protégé, who must share a voluntary and reciprocal relationship to facilitate the mentoring process. It also incorporates an interpersonal process, which describes the dynamic and interactive relationship between the mentor and the mentee. This encompasses communication, building trust, emotional intelligence, active listening, empathy and support, etc. The mentoring antecedents also include cultural awareness because the professional domains are made of individuals from different walk of-life and diverse cultural and racial backgrounds. Also emphasized within the antecedents is training, given that effective mentor training significantly enhances mentoring outcomes. Backed by the literature, the variable – organisational or institutional support, identified as a central antecedent in the mentoring process was added by the authors to achieve the purpose of this study. As significant stakeholder, an organization’s culture, policies, and infrastructure provide a critical foundation for mentoring, influencing the availability of resources, support, and opportunities for mentorship to thrive (Giacumo et al., 2020).

Criteria or mentoring activities include sharing of knowledge and experiences from mentor to protégé. This comprises teaching, coaching and facilitation of learning. It also involves providing emotional support. Highlighting the psychosocial function of mentoring, this criterion emphasizes providing supports, encouragement, building morale, and the accepting aspects of mentoring, espoused by the foremost scholars in the mentoring research, e.g., Ragins and Kram (2007). Role-modeling criterion bears on the social roles and behaviours which are learned through observational learning, i.e., by observing the mentor. The guiding criterion consists of counseling, advising, and networking. The roles of mentoring in fostering these criteria have been documented in the literature (e.g., Bello & Mansour, 2013; Olatokun & Njideaka, 2021).

Consequences or outcomes criterion includes increased self-confidence of the mentee; maximized learning, which a mentor achieves through the combination of teaching, coaching, role-modeling, provision of relevant learning opportunities, and sharing personal experiences; increased scholastic and career satisfaction; and promotion of personal and professional growth (Mijares, Baxley, & Bond, 2013).

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. What are the mentoring strategies through which the library staffs were mentored?
2. What is the effectiveness of the mentoring antecedents?
3. What is the extent of practice of the mentoring criteria or activities?
4. What is the library staff's perception of the consequences or outcomes of mentoring?
5. What are the challenges to effective mentoring in the library?
6. What are the ways of overcoming challenges to effective mentoring?

Methodology

This study was underpinned by the positivist research paradigm which aligns with quantitative research method. A survey design was adopted for this study. The study's population comprised all the 20 Library staff of Nigerian Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria. Survey questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. 20 copies of the questionnaire were distributed among the 20 staff. However, 18 copies representing 90% response rate were returned and found usable for the study. A self-designed questionnaire titled; Mentoring Experience Questionnaire (MEQ) which consisted 78 items was used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into seven (7) sections A to G. Section A focused on demographic information of the respondents such as gender, age, rank, work experience, and academic qualification. Section B consisted of 12 items that measured mentoring strategies used in mentoring library staff, Section C consisted of 10 items that measured effectiveness of mentoring antecedents, Section D consisted of 14 items that measured the extent of practice of mentoring activities; Section E consisted of 15 items that measured Library staff members' perception of the consequences or outcome of mentoring; Section F consisted of 12 items that measured challenges associated with mentoring; while Section G consisted of 10 items that measured the ways of overcoming mentoring challenges all on a 4-points Likert scale from Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 to Strongly Agree (SA) = 4. The instrument was validated by professionals in the field of Library and Information Science at Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, who scrutinized and approved the content adequacy and comprehensiveness of the questionnaire items before data collection exercise. The reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot study carried out among the library personnel in Abdullahi Fodiyo Library, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, in which the data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha statistics calculated on Statistical Package for Social the Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The Cronbach's alpha value obtained was 0.893, which was adequately high, indicating that the instrument had acceptable reliability coefficient, and is therefore suitable for the study.

Results

In this section, data were presented in line with the research objectives. The distribution of the study's population and the demographic information are shown in Table 1 below. The data collected were analysed electronically on SPSS version 23.0 using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the results are presented one after the other in tables for clear understanding.

Table 1: Distribution of Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demography	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	15	83.3%
	Female	3	16.7%
Age	21 – 30 years	2	11.1%
	31 – 40 years	8	44.4%
	41 – 50 years	6	33.3%
	51 – 60 years	1	5.6%
	Above 60 years	1	5.6%
Rank	Library Office Cadres	8	44.4%
	Graduate Assistant	1	5.6%
	Librarian II	3	16.7%
	Librarian I	3	16.7%
	Senior Librarian	2	11.1%
	Deputy University Librarian	1	5.6%
Work Experience	1 - 5years	4	22.2%
	6 -10years	9	50.0%
	11 - 15years	3	16.7%
	21years +	2	11.1%
Qualification	ND	3	16.7%
	HND	2	11.1%
	BLIS	5	27.8%
	PGD	1	5.6%
	MLIS	5	27.8%
	Ph.D	2	11.1%

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 1 revealed analysis of demographic information of the respondents in the study in which the analysis of Gender of the respondents showed that 15 (83.3%) respondents are male and 3 (16.7%) are female; while the analysis of the Age in years of the respondents revealed that 2(11.1%) are between 21 – 30 years old, 8(44.4%) are between 31 – 40 years old; 6(33.3%) are between 41 – 50 years old; 1(5.6%) was between 51 – 60 years old, and 1(5.6%) was above 60 years old. In addition, the analysis of ranks of the respondents showed that 8(44.4%) were in the Library Officer cadre; 1(5.6%) was a Graduate Assistant; 3(16.7%) are Librarian II; 3(16.7%) are Librarian I; 2(11.1%) are Senior Librarians and 1(5.6%) was the Deputy University Librarian. The analysis of Work Experience of the respondents revealed that 4(22.2%) have 1 – 5 years of experience; 9(50%) have 6 – 10 years of experience; 3(16.7%) have 11 – 15 years of experience, while 2(11.1%) have above 20 years of experience in the profession. Nonetheless, the results of highest qualification obtained revealed that 3(16.7%) hold (National Diploma (ND)); 2(11.1%) hold Higher National Diploma (HND); 5(27.8%) hold Bachelor of Library Science (BLIS) degree; 1(5.6%) holds Post-Graduate Diploma (PGD); 5(27.8%) hold Master of Library and Information Science (MLIS) degree, while 2(11.1%) hold a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D) degree.

Table 2: Mentoring Programmes and mentored Library Staffs in Nigerian Police Academy Wudil, Kano State

Table with 10 columns: SN, Mentoring Strategies through which Library Staff were Mentored, SD, D, A, SA, Mean, Std. Dev, Decision. It lists 12 mentoring strategies and their corresponding data points, ending with a total row.

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

The result in Table 2 shows the mean range for the responses on mentoring strategies used in Mentoring Library Staff members. Items 1,2,3,4,5,7,8,9,10 and12, had their mean above the

significant mean of 3.10 while items 6 and 11 had their mean below the significant mean value of 3.10. The item above the significant mean indicate that; Junior library staff willingly seek advice and guidance from the experienced librarians anytime; Experienced library staff willingly advise and guide the junior staff as the need may arise; Library staff are exposed to various aspect of the profession through staff rotation; Orientation programmes are usually organized for new library staff upon assumption of duty; Library staff attend professional conferences, workshops and seminars to share knowledge with colleagues from other libraries; Experienced librarians pair to collaborate on professional issues like research, sharing information on conferences, seminars and workshops; Less experienced librarians are paired with experienced ones for their professional development; Short-term trainings are usually organized to respond to a particular situation or solve a particular problem; Through social media and other online platforms, library staff seek guidance and support from other librarians in distant libraries; and Supervisors, e.g., unit/departmental heads provide training and guidance for their subordinates all had their mean value greater than the cluster mean were all accepted as mentoring strategies used in were. However, the two mentoring strategies;Library staff seek advice and guidance from professional colleagues in other libraries and Junior staff train the senior staff on new technologies were rejected as being used in the study area. Therefore, this demonstrated that there were adequate mentoring strategies employed in mentoring library staff in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano state, Nigeria.

Table 3: Effectiveness of Mentoring Antecedents among Library Staff in Nigerian Police Academy Wudil, Kano State

	Effectiveness of the Mentoring Antecedents	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	Our senior staff have the necessary expertise in the profession and share their knowledge with the junior staff	0	2	10	6	3.22	0.65	Accepted
2	My library has knowledgeable mentors who are willing to share wisdom and experience, and the mentees who want the mentor's guidance and support.	1	3	8	6	3.06	0.87	Accepted
3	My organization fully supports the mentoring strategies which are already in place	4	3	6	5	2.67	1.14	Accepted
4	My mentor is always approachable and accessible whenever I need his guidance	0	3	7	8	3.28	0.75	Accepted
5	My organization has well-developed and structured policy for mentoring activities to flourish	2	7	9	0	2.39	0.70	Rejected
6	I always feel comfortable sharing my problems and concerns with my mentor	0	4	5	9	3.28	0.83	Accepted

7	My organization has well-structured mentoring programmes for staff development	4	11	3	1	1.94	0.64	Rejected
8	My mentor has a positive attitude towards mentoring	1	1	8	8	3.28	0.83	Accepted
9	My mentor and I are willing to share voluntary and reciprocal relationship which is necessary for mentoring to occur.	0	3	5	10	3.39	0.78	Accepted
10	There is recognition for cultural inclusiveness and diversity in our mentoring relationships.	2	3	7	6	2.94	1.00	Accepted
Average						2.95	0.82	Accepted

Sources: *Fieldwork (2025)*

Table 3 showed the responses on the effectiveness of the mentoring antecedents in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State. The table revealed that eight mentoring antecedents; items 1,2,3,4, 6,8,9,out of the ten were effective among the library staff members of Nigerian Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, with each item having a mean score greater than the threshold of 2.50, indicating that the items were accepted as effective antecedents; while only two antecedents items 5 and 7 had mean ratings less than the threshold of 2.50 were rejected by the respondents. However, the overall Grand Mean of 2.95 with a Standard Deviation of 0.82 (i.e. Mean = 2.95, SD = 0.82) was greater than the threshold Mean of 2.50, indicating that the respondents unanimously agreed that the mentoring antecedents were effective in mentoring the library staff members at Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria. These accepted antecedents include: Our senior staff have the necessary expertise in the profession and share their knowledge with the junior staff , My library has knowledgeable mentors who are willing to share wisdom and experience, and the mentees who want the mentor's guidance and support; My organization fully supports the mentoring strategies which are already in place; My mentor is always approachable and accessible whenever I need his guidance; I always feel comfortable sharing my problems and concerns with my mentor; My mentor has a positive attitude towards mentoring; My mentor and I are willing to share voluntary and reciprocal relationship which is necessary for mentoring to occur; and There is recognition for cultural inclusiveness and diversity in our mentoring relationships; while the two rejected antecedents were: My organization has well-developed and structured policy for mentoring activities to flourish and My organization has well-structured mentoring programmes for staff development. Therefore, this revealed that the mentoring antecedents available in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil Library, Kano state, Nigeria are effective.

Table 4: Extent of Practice of the Mentoring Activities among Library Staff in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State

Table with 9 columns: SN, Extent of Practice of Mentoring Activities, VL, L, H, VH, Mean, Std. Dev, Extent. It lists 14 mentoring activities and their corresponding scores and overall averages.

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 4 showed the responses on the extent of practice of the mentoring activities by the library staff members. The table revealed that 13, out of the 14 items i.e., items 1 to 13 measuring the extent of practice of mentoring activities in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State have their mean scores lying between the thresholds of 2.51 – 3.25, indicating that the items were rated as “High” extent; while only item 14 whose mean score was between the thresholds of 1.76 – 2.50 was rated “Low” extent by the respondents. The overall Grand Mean of 2.81, with a Standard Deviation of 0.71 (i.e. Mean = 2.81, SD = 0.71) indicated that the respondents unanimously agreed that there was “High” extent of practice of mentoring activities among library staff members of Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria. The high extent mentoring practices are: Knowledge and experience sharing; Teaching; Provision of career and professional supports; Coaching; Facilitation of Learning; Provision of Emotional supports, e.g., Showing care and affection to subordinate staff that are in need; Encouragements; Morale building; Open-minded guidance ; Role-modeling e.g., inculcating leadership skills, conflict resolution skills, team collaboration spirit, emotional intelligence, critical thinking skills, etc; Guidance ; Counseling; ;

and Advising; while only Networking e.g., introducing and connecting junior colleagues to important persons in the profession was rated Low extent by the respondents. Therefore, this suggests that there was High extent practice of mentoring activities among the library staff of Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano state, Nigeria.

Research Question 4: What is the library staff members’ perception of the consequences/outcomes of mentoring?

Table 5: Library Staff Members’ Perception of the Consequences or Outcomes of Mentoring in Nigerian Police Academy Wudil Library, Kano State

SN	Library Staff's Perception of the Consequences of Mentoring.	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	Mentoring has improved my job satisfaction	0	1	5	12	3.61	0.61	Accepted
2	I have gained valuable skills and knowledge through mentoring.	0	0	4	14	3.78	0.43	Accepted
3	Mentoring has enhanced my career advancement opportunities.	0	1	3	14	3.72	0.58	Accepted
4	My confidence in performing tasks has increased due to mentoring.	0	2	5	11	3.50	0.71	Accepted
5	Mentoring has improved my problem-solving skills.	1	1	9	7	3.22	0.81	Accepted
6	I have developed a stronger professional network through mentoring.	1	6	2	9	3.06	1.06	Accepted
7	Mentoring has helped to reduce my job stress and anxiety levels.	0	3	7	8	3.28	0.75	Accepted
8	My overall well-being has improved due to mentoring	1	5	7	5	2.89	0.90	Accepted
9	Mentoring has increased my motivation to learn	1	1	7	9	3.33	0.84	Accepted
10	Mentoring has improved my communication skills and abilities	1	2	9	6	3.11	0.83	Accepted
11	I have gained a better understanding of professional trends through mentoring	1	1	5	11	3.44	0.86	Accepted
12	My leadership skills have improved due to mentoring	1	1	4	12	3.50	0.86	Accepted
13	Mentoring has positively impacted my overall career development.	1	1	2	14	3.61	0.85	Accepted
14	I have experienced increased career and scholastic satisfaction due to mentoring.	1	0	7	10	3.44	0.78	Accepted
15	My personal and professional growth has improved due to mentoring.	1	0	4	13	3.61	0.78	Accepted
						3.41	0.78	Accepted

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 5 showed the responses on their perception of the consequences or outcome of the mentoring activities in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria. The table revealed that all the

15 items assessing the consequences or outcomes of mentoring activities among the library staff in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria have mean ratings greater than the threshold mean of 2.50, indicating that all the items were accepted by the respondents. Similarly, the overall Grand Mean of 3.41, with a Standard Deviation of 0.78 (i.e. Mean = 3.41, SD = 0.78) was also greater than the threshold Mean of 2.50, indicating that the respondents unanimously accepted all the 15 consequences or outcomes of mentoring at Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria, which include: Mentoring has improved my job satisfaction; I have gained valuable skills and knowledge through mentoring; Mentoring has enhanced my career advancement opportunities; My confidence in performing tasks has increased due to mentoring; Mentoring has improved my problem-solving skills; I have developed a stronger professional network through mentoring; Mentoring has helped to reduce my job stress and anxiety levels; My overall well-being has improved due to mentoring ; Mentoring has increased my motivation to learn; Mentoring has improved my communication skills and abilities; I have gained a better understanding of professional trends through mentoring; My leadership skills have improved due to mentoring; Mentoring has positively impacted my overall career development; I have experienced increased career and scholastic satisfaction due to mentoring; and My personal and professional growth has improved due to mentoring. Therefore, this indicates that the library staff members of Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State have a positive perception of the consequences or outcomes of mentoring.

Table 6: Challenges to Effective Mentoring of the Library Staff in Nigerian Police Academy Wudil, Kano State

SN	Challenges Associated with Mentoring	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	There is no well-structured organizational policy framework supporting mentoring activities in the library	1	1	7	9	3.33	0.84	Accepted
2	There is lack of well-structured mentoring programmes in the library	2	4	2	10	3.11	1.13	Accepted
3	Senior staff lack mentoring expertise and skills needed to mentor the junior staff	5	10	3	0	1.89	0.68	Rejected
4	Library staff generally show negative attitude towards mentoring	6	7	4	1	2.00	0.91	Rejected
5	Senior staff criticize their subordinates unconstructively	6	8	3	1	1.94	0.87	Rejected
6	There is lack of mutual trust and confidentiality among both the mentors and the mentee.	6	7	3	2	2.06	1.00	Rejected
7	Some senior staff are always unwilling to share their knowledge and expertise with the junior staff.	3	7	7	1	2.33	0.84	Rejected

8	Mentors and the mentees do not keep to the goals and objectives of the mentoring relationship.	4	11	1	2	2.06	0.87	Rejected
9	Some junior staff are timid and hence, do not communicate openly during interactions.	4	0	8	6	2.89	1.13	Accepted
10	Mentoring is not a clearly defined aspect of our library’s organisational culture.	2	4	9	3	2.72	0.89	Accepted
11	Inordinate emotional feeling, e.g., sexual relationships which often result from uncontrolled mentoring relationships,	14	3	1	0	1.28	0.57	Rejected
12	Junior staff at times display insubordination, which impacts mentoring relationship negatively.	2	5	9	2	2.61	0.85	Accepted
Average						2.23	0.90	Rejected

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 6 showed the responses on the challenges to effective mentoring among the library staff members of Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State. The table revealed that 5 items (1, 2, 9, 10, and 12) out of the 12 challenges to effective mentoring activities have mean ratings greater than the threshold of 2.50, as assessed by Library staffs in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria, which indicated that the 5 the items: there is no well-structured organizational policy framework supporting mentoring activities in the library, there is lack of well-structured mentoring programmes in the library, some junior staff are timid and hence do not communicate openly during interactions, mentoring is not a clearly defined aspect of our library’s organisational culture, and Junior staff at times display insubordination which impacts mentoring relationship negatively, were accepted as challenges to effective mentoring among the Library staff members at Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State. However, 7 other challenges (senior staff lack mentoring expertise and skills needed to mentor the junior staff, library staff generally show negative attitude towards mentoring, senior staff criticize their subordinates unconstructively, there is lack of mutual trust and confidentially among both the mentors and the mentee, some senior staff are always unwilling to share their knowledge and expertise with the junior staff, mentors and the mentees do not keep to the goals and objectives of the mentoring relationship ‘and inordinate emotional feeling, e.g., sexual relationships which often result from uncontrolled mentoring relationship), which mean ratings were less than the threshold of 2.50 were rejected by the respondents. In addition, the overall Grand Mean of 2.23 with a Standard Deviation of 0.90 (i.e. Mean = 2.23, SD = 0.90) was less than the threshold Mean of 2.50, indicating that the respondents rejected that there were many challenges to effective mentoring of Library staff members in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria. This therefore implies that there were negligible challenges to effective mentoring of the library staff members in Nigerian Police Academy Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria.

Table 7: Ways of Overcoming Challenges to Effective Mentoring of Library Staff in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State

	Ways of Overcoming Mentoring Challenges	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	There should be institutional policy that supports mentoring activities	0	1	4	13	3.67	0.59	Accepted
2	The library should have well-structured mentoring programmes	1	0	1	16	3.78	0.73	Accepted
3	Library management should regularly organize staff orientation to educate staff on the benefits of mentoring	0	1	2	15	3.72	0.75	Accepted
4	Mentors and mentees should be willing to listen and learn from each other	0	1	2	15	3.78	0.55	Accepted
5	The individuals involved in the mentoring relationship should have mutual respect and trust	0	1	1	16	3.83	0.52	Accepted
6	Regular trainings should be organized for both mentors and mentees on mentoring relationship.	0	0	2	16	3.89	0.32	Accepted
7	There should be clearly defined roles and responsibilities in the mentoring relationships.	1	0	1	16	3.78	0.73	Accepted
8	The mentor and the mentee should have good interpersonal and professional skills.	2	0	2	14	3.56	0.98	Accepted
9	Boundaries and time for the relationship between the mentor and the mentee should be clearly and defined.	0	2	2	14	3.67	0.69	Accepted
10	The objectives /expectation of the mentoring relationship should be made specific and clear.	0	0	2	16	3.89	0.32	Accepted
	Average					3.76	0.62	Accepted

Sources: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 7 revealed the responses on the ways of overcoming challenges to effective mentoring. The table revealed that all the 10 items assessing the ways of overcoming challenges to effective mentoring among the Library staff in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State have mean ratings greater than the threshold mean of 2.50, indicating that all the items were accepted by the respondents as valid ways of overcoming the challenges. Similarly, the overall Grand Mean of 3.76 with a Standard Deviation of 0.62 (i.e. Mean = 3.76, SD = 0.62) was also greater than the threshold Mean of 2.50, indicating that the respondents unanimously accepted all the 10 ways of addressing challenges to effective mentoring of library staff members at Nigeria Police Academy

Wudil, Kano State. The items include: There should be institutional policy that supports mentoring activities; The library should have well-structured mentoring programmes; Library management should regularly organize staff orientation to educate staff on the benefits of mentoring; Mentors and mentees should be willing to listen and learn from each other; The individuals involved in the mentoring relationship should have mutual respect and There should be clearly defined roles and responsibilities in the mentoring relationships; The mentor and the mentee should have good interpersonal and professional skills; Boundaries and time for the relationship between the mentor and the mentee should be clearly and defined; and the objectives /expectation of the mentoring relationship should be made specific and clear. This therefore signifies that the library staff members of Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano state, Nigeria are aware of several ways of addressing challenges to effective mentoring of library staff members in the Institution.

Discussion of Findings

This study examines the mentoring experiences of library staff of Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano. Findings revealed the library staff members in Nigerian Police Academy, Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria have experienced ten different mentoring strategies as follows: Junior library staff willingly seek advice and guidance from the experienced librarians anytime; Experienced library staff willingly advise and guide the junior staff as the need may arise; Library staff are exposed to various aspect of the profession through staff rotation; Orientation programmes are usually organized for new library staff upon assumption of duty; Library staff attend professional conferences, workshops and seminars to share knowledge with colleagues from other libraries; Experienced librarians pair to collaborate on professional issues like research, sharing information on conferences, seminars and workshops; Less experienced librarians are paired with experienced ones for their professional development; Short-term trainings are usually organized to respond to a particular situation or solve a particular problem; Through social media and other online platforms, library staff seek guidance and support from other librarians in distant libraries; and Supervisors, e.g., unit/departmental heads provide training and guidance for their subordinates.

This result corroborates the findings of previous studies (e.g. Nkamnebe, Oladokun & Jorosi, 2025a), which reported librarians' exposure to various mentoring programmes in South-East Nigeria. This finding also supports other related studies (Nwabueze & Anike, 2016; Idoko, Ugwuanyi, & Osadebe, 2016) which reported that library personnel in some federal universities across Nigeria have experienced a wide-range of mentoring initiatives. This was demonstrated by their overwhelming agreement to most of the descriptor statements which sought to find out the mentoring initiatives they have experienced. This finding implies that mentoring is a valued skill development intervention strategy in the library. It also suggests that efforts must have been made by the library management to support staff development. Ultimately, it is an indication that the library personnel have opportunities for growth and learning.

However, participants conceded non-exposure to external mentoring (i.e., seeking advice and guidance from professional colleagues from other libraries). This is suggestive of lack of awareness, limited networking opportunities, or preference for internal support systems. In addition, the staff admitted non-exposure to reverse mentoring (i.e., junior staff training the senior staff on new technologies, while the senior staffs transfer professional experience to the junior staff). Many factors could have accounted for this outcome, e.g., traditional mentoring mindset,

i.e., the traditional view of mentoring, which always considers the mentee as a sole benefactor in a mentoring relationship. Moreover, it may be connected to the hierarchical culture. A hierarchical organisational culture may discourage reverse mentoring, as this tends to challenge traditional power dynamics.

Findings further revealed that respondents have a positive perception of the effectiveness of the mentoring antecedents in their organisation, given that they expressed agreement with 8 out of the 10 descriptor statements connected to this. The statement: “My mentor and I are willing to share voluntary and reciprocal relationship, which is necessary for mentoring to occur” has the highest mean rating (M=3.39). This is suggestive of the participants’ willingness to participate in mentoring activities, aligning with the postulation of Mijares, Baxley, and Bond (2013), which emphasized that both the mentor and the mentee must demonstrate the willingness to go into a mentoring relationship for the best outcomes to be achieved. This was followed by the descriptor statements: “My mentor is always approachable and accessible whenever I need his guidance” (M=3.28), “I always feel comfortable sharing my problems and concerns with my mentor” (M=3.28), and “My mentor has a positive attitude towards mentoring” (M=3.28). These imply that the mentoring antecedents such as approachability, accessibility, good rapport, availability of mentors willing to mentor appear to be robust and conducive to open communications.

My organization has well-developed and structured policy for mentoring activities to flourish was rated low (M=2.39). This was followed by another statement: “My organization has well-structured mentoring programmes for staff development”, which has the least mean rating (M=1.94). Taken together, these suggested there is a gap to be filled in the organisational structure and policy, which should provide a strong framework and guidelines for mentoring programmes. This somewhat contradicts the participants’ positive perception of the mentoring antecedents. Be that as it may, the positive perception of the mentoring antecedents earlier reported could have stemmed from the informal mentoring method and personal relationships among staff, which may have compensated for the inadequacy in the formal system’s support. This finding implies that mentoring experiences of the staff tend to be more informal than formal, corroborating the finding of Idoko, Ugwuanyi and Osadebe (2016), and Nwabueze and Anike (2016), Olatokun and Njideaka (2021), which had earlier reported prevalence of informal types of mentoring in federal university libraries across Nigeria.

Furthermore, on extent of practice of mentoring criteria/activities, findings revealed that almost all the practices embodied by the mentoring activities, as represented by the descriptor statements were rated positively. The overall average mean rating of Mean = 2.81, SD = 0.71 indicates that mentoring activities are practiced to a high extent, with morale building ranking top, followed by encouragement. This finding aligns with result of Tan (2016), which identified morale building as one of the roles of mentoring. The result also supports Iqbal’s (2020) observation that mentors support their mentees by motivating and encouraging them, and by so doing, strengthen them in their areas of weaknesses. These emphasize the psychosocial functions of mentoring, advocated by foremost scholars in mentoring research (e.g., Kram, 1986; Ragins&Kram, 2007). The psychosocial functions of mentoring help the mentee in building confidence, self-esteem, and overall well-being. However, the descriptor statement: “Networking e.g., introducing and connecting junior colleagues to important persons in the profession” has the least Mean Rating. This shows that the participants’ mentoring criterion is deficient in this context, despite its

importance in the participant's career. Networking is an important aspect of career development function of mentoring, which helps mentees to advance in their careers by helping them establish connections and relationship with influential people in the profession, access new opportunities and resources, and gain exposure to new ideas and perspectives.

Additionally, findings revealed that library staffs have positive perception of the consequences or outcomes of their mentoring experiences. The descriptor statement: "I have gained valuable skills and knowledge through mentoring" has the higher mean rating, followed by the statement: "Mentoring has enhanced my career advancement opportunities". The statement: "My overall well-being has improved due to mentoring" has the least mean rating. Altogether, these attest to their assurance that mentoring has had a positive impact on their personal and professional lives. Hence, they are likely to be motivated for continued participation in mentoring relationships, and are more likely to seek out future mentoring opportunities. This result is consistent with findings of various studies. For instance, Freedman (2021) reported that benefits accruable from mentoring experiences include: career advice and support, long lasting professional relationship, role modeling, provision of resources and opportunities. The finding is also congruent with those of Nkamnebe, Oladokun, and Jorosi (2025a), Nkamnebe, Oladokun, and Jorosi (2025b), which recorded a positive influence of exposure to mentoring on cognitive behaviours, e.g., self-efficacy belief in cataloguing, outcome expectation belief in cataloguing, and performance outcome, such as skill development in cataloguing. The finding also confirms those of other scholars (e.g., Bello & Mansor, 2013; Olatokun & Njideaka, 2021; Popoola, Iyoro, & Ogungbo, 2022), which had earlier reported various consequences or outcomes of mentoring, which include: skill development, career development, professional development, career satisfaction, self-confidence, excellent work performance, etc.

Findings also revealed issues which constitute challenges to effective mentoring in Nigeria Police Academy Wudil Library, Kano State. These were expressed in terms of: absence of well-structured organizational policy framework supporting mentoring activities in the library, lack of well-structured mentoring programmes in the library, timidity of some junior staff leading to inability to communicate openly during interactions, mentoring not being a clearly defined aspect of the library's organisational culture, junior staff's display of insubordination which impacts mentoring relationship negatively. These all have mean ratings above 2.50, indicating agreement. Three issues (absence of well-structured organizational policy framework supporting mentoring activities in the library, lack of well-structured mentoring programmes in the library, and mentoring not being a clearly defined aspect of the library's organisational culture) are closely linked to organisational support, which is a necessary requirement for effective mentoring; while the issues of timidity and insubordination of junior staff constitute personal factors. This finding confirms results of studies by Nwabueze and Anike (2016), and Idoko, Ugwuanyi and Osadebe (2016), Nwankwor, Ike and Anozie (2017) which respectively reported similar challenges associated with mentoring of library personnel in Nigerian universities.

Findings further revealed the library staffs' recognition of possible ways of overcoming the challenges associated with effective mentoring. Among these are: regular trainings for mentors and mentees on mentoring relationship; and the specificity and clarity of objectives or expectations of the mentoring relationship are paramount. This implies that the library staffs acknowledged

existence of challenges in mentoring, and may likely take proactive steps to address or mitigate the effects of the challenges.

Conclusion

This study explored the mentoring experiences of library staff at the Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study concludes that the staff members of Nigeria Police Academy Wudil Library, Kano have a positive perception of their mentoring experiences. To elaborate further, the findings revealed that the library staff had experienced a variety of mentoring strategies, although they reported little exposure to external and reverse mentoring strategies. Furthermore, participants expressed a positive perception about the effectiveness of the mentoring antecedents within their organization.

The finding highlighted two significant gaps, which include respondents' refutation that: their organization has well-developed and structured policy for mentoring activities to flourish, and that their organization has well-structured mentoring programmes for staff development. Given the specialized skills required in security-focused library services, absence of policy and structured mentoring strategies can hinder the professional growth and confidence of staff, thereby impacting negatively on the quality of information services provided to students, faculty members, researchers and other users. Although mentoring activities were practiced to a high degree, there were notable deficiencies in areas such as networking, specifically in terms of introducing and connecting junior staff to influential professionals within the field.

Furthermore, respondents have positive perception of the outcomes of the mentoring they have experienced, thus acknowledging the impacts on their personal, career, and professional developments. The findings also revealed that members of the library staff are aware of several challenges to effective mentoring in their library, which among others include absence of well-structured organizational policy framework supporting mentoring activities in the library. Finally, the respondents agreed that there are several ways to address or overcome challenges to effective mentoring of library staff members in the Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the study recommends as follows:

1. Although the staff members of the library have experienced ten different mentoring strategies, it is recommended that external and reverse mentoring strategies should also be explored and implemented to broaden staff development and foster cross-generational knowledge sharing.
2. It is recommended that the library should develop a formal mentoring policy and establish structured mentoring programmes to support staff development, building on the existing effective mentoring antecedents.
3. To further leverage mentoring, the library should implement strategies to enhance networking opportunities, connecting staff with accomplished professionals in the field. This will help the library staff to build valuable connections, enhancing their career growth and contributing to the library's overall success. For instance, incorporating networking

opportunities into mentoring activities, such as frequent sponsorship to workshops, seminars, conferences and related events is necessary, so as to facilitate connections and relationships with important persons in the profession.

4. The library should build on the positive perception of mentoring by promoting its benefits, sharing success stories and further integrating mentoring into staff development strategies.
5. To overcome the existing mentoring challenges, it is recommended that the library should have well-structured organizational policy framework supporting mentoring activities within the library, develop structured mentoring programmes in the library, implement trainings to boost junior staff confidence and communication skills, integrate mentoring into the organisational culture, and establish guidelines for managing relationships.
6. Overall, the library should adopt and implement the identified strategies, ensuring they are tailored to address specific challenges and support effective mentoring.

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